

Epi-fluorescent microscopy of edge trimmed carbon fibre reinforced polymer: an alternative to CT-scanning

S. Ashworth, The University of Sheffield

1. Current surface quality metrics

Carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) surface quality can be measured using areal measurement methods such as focus variation to gather surface topography information (Figure 1) and metrics. Whilst useful, current metrics are based on metallic quality measurements which may not be suitable for anisotropic CFRP which have specific machining defects.

Figure 1 – Surface topography of edge trimmed CFRP

Are current methods able to capture all the defects associated with CFRP machining?

2. The need for sub-surface metrics

Figure 2 – Smeared matrix of edge trimmed CFRP

Matrix smearing occurs when the heat from the friction in the cutting process exceeds the glass transition (T_g) of the matrix material. This softer matrix can then be pushed across the milled surface by the tool during the feed process. Fibres oriented at +45 and 90° to the cutting edge are particularly susceptible to matrix smearing (Figure 2).

Matrix smearing may be hiding defects beneath the machined CFRP surface.

3. Seeing beyond the surface

X-ray computed tomography (XCT) is a suitable method to observe machining sub-surface defects (Figure 3) but this is expensive in terms of time and cost of scanning. In addition, low powered machines may cause artefacts and often are not able to resolve defects to fibre diameter.

Figure 3 – Observation of through depth defects

Epi-fluorescence is a high resolution, low cost alternative to XCT to observe through-depth machining defects with a novel damage metric.

4. The method – epi-fluorescent microscopy

1. Trim a CFRP sample as per Figure 3, set in fluorescent resin (see above samples), observe through-depth defects using an epi-fluorescent microscope, Figure 4, a).
2. Crop to region of interest including the definition of a theoretically straight cut edge and change to greyscale, Figure 4, b).
3. Use automatic Otsu image thresholding to show only fluorescing pixels in a binary image, Figure 4, c). Highlighted pixels can then be used to determine a new damage metric.

Figure 4 – a) optical fluorescent image, b) greyscale image and c) binary image showing machining damage

5. Novel metric applied to Fabric and UD CFRP

Figure 5 – Damage shown through binary images of fabric and UD milled CFRP

Figure 5 shows sub-surface damage for edge trimmed fabric and UD materials where fibres are at 0, +45, 90 and -45° to the cutting edge.

Fibres at 90° to the cutting edge have most damage followed by fabric material.

Validation against XCT shows the epi-fluorescent method is accurately capturing machining defects.

The binary images and novel metric of the new method capture important sub-surface damage of CFRP milling.

Figure 6 – Quantity of damage for differing fibre orientations to the cutting edge

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